

GEOMETRICAL LIMITATIONS TO THE HOMOGENEOUS MIXING OF METAL AND CERAMIC POWDERS ON FABRICATING Al MATRIX/SiC COMPOSITES

H. Carvalhinhos, T. Marcelo and M. H. Carvalho
Instituto Nacional de Engenharia e Tecnologia Industrial
1699 Lisboa Codex, Portugal

ABSTRACT

A geometrical model has been worked out which allows to evaluate the effect of the relative particle sizes of the metal (D) and the ceramic powders (d) and the volume fraction of the ceramic on the homogeneity of their mixtures for the production of sound powder metallurgy MMC's. The model refers to spherical particles and assumes that the harder ceramic particles distribute themselves uniformly on the surface of the metal particles. The microstructures and tensile properties of several SiC/Al composites covering different D/d ratios are presented as examples and demonstrate the usefulness of the model.

INTRODUCTION

Blending of metallic and ceramic powders in order to obtain mixtures of good homogeneity proves to be one of the crucial steps in fabricating MMC's of improved properties. Therefore parameters like mixing equipment, time and energy of mixing, use of enhancers and others have been the subject of considerable attention by researchers [1,2]. Volume fractions and particle distributions are of course included in these parameters but perhaps no serious consideration has yet been given to the limitations imposed on these parameters by their interrelated effect on the quality of the mixture. In fact assuming that the technique used for mixing successfully manages to desaggregate the particles and evenly distribute them, it is still to be known whether the volume fractions and particle distributions chosen are compatible with the result of a final mixture without frequent agglomerations of ceramic particles which are sources of porosity.

One obvious limitation stems from the consideration that for a certain volume fraction of ceramic particles and a well defined metallic particle diameter, the finer the ceramic particles the less space will be available on the surface of the metal particles to accommodate the ceramic. A ceramic particle size will ultimately be reached below which the particles will have to form aggregates in order to comply with the chosen volume fraction. Attempts to further decrease the particle size will only result in worse properties for the composite, particularly its mechanical properties.

This paper introduces a simple geometrical model which quantifies the interrelation between particle diameters and volume fractions serving as a guide to the range of mixtures that are more adequate to the purpose of obtaining uniform distribution. A comparison of its predictions with the results of practical examples is also included.

A MODEL

The model applies to a mixture of metallic and ceramic spherical particles of uniform diameters D and d respectively. Blending is supposed to uniformly distribute the ceramic particles on the metal particle surfaces; consolidation, by compaction and sintering, hot pressing or extrusion, forces the ceramic particles to indent in the softer metal particles and therefore the volume fraction of ceramic in the composite is given by:

$$V = \frac{\frac{n \cdot V_{cp}}{2}}{V_{mp} + \frac{n \cdot V_{cp}}{2}} = \frac{1}{\frac{2 \delta^3}{n} + 1} \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of ceramic particles scattered on the metal particle surface, of which only half the volume is embedded on the softer particle, the other half being embedded in the nearest neighbour metal particle ($\delta = D/d$ and V_{mp} and V_{cp} are the metal and ceramic particles volume, respectively).

If to each ceramic particle corresponds a spherical segment of diameter L (average distance between ceramic particles) on the metallic particle surface, the area reserved to each ceramic particle is:

$$a = \pi D h \quad (2)$$

where h is the height of the spherical segment. As

$$\left(\frac{D}{2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{L}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{D}{2} - h\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

then

$$h = \frac{D - \sqrt{D^2 - L^2}}{2} \quad (4)$$

Substituting Eqn (4) into Eqn (2) gives:

$$a = \pi D \frac{D - \sqrt{D^2 - L^2}}{2} \quad (5)$$

The number of ceramic particles scattered on the surface of the metal particles will then be:

Volume fraction	(D/d) _{min}	(D/d) _{max}
5%	2.3	17
10%	1.7	8
15%	1.6	5
20%	1.5	3.4
25%	1.5	2.4
30%	-	-

Obviously the narrower the window, the more difficult it will be to obtain a reasonable mixture. The criterium chosen of $L/d > 1.5$ would, in general, eliminate any possibility of adding 30% or more of ceramic to the metal powder without the formation of ceramic agglomerates.

This is an important consideration in the practical situation for which the powders are characterized by a distribution of particle sizes rather than by a single and uniform value. The narrower the window (i.e. the higher the volume fraction) the narrower the particle size distribution has to be in order to yield mixtures with less agglomerates and porosity sources.

EXPERIMENTAL

A variety of aluminium powders and SiC particles have been used in the in-house fabrication of PM SiC reinforced Al alloys matrix composites [3-5]. The aluminium powders included alloyed Al 2014 and Al 6061 as well as non alloyed powders such as Alumix 321 AS081 and 321 AS91; the SiC grits were F600, F800 and F1200 and the reinforcement volume fraction varied between 0.1 and 0.2. Typical morphologies of the aluminium and SiC particles are shown in Fig. 2.

Cumulative particle size distributions of the aluminium powders and SiC particulates were determined by a laser method. The mean particle diameter (D_{50} and d_{50} respectively for metal and ceramic particles) of the raw materials as well as the correspondent D/d ratios for the composites produced are summarized in Table 1.

Blending of the composite mixtures was carried out in a Turbula tumbler for different periods of time which varied between 1 and 4h, depending on the raw materials.

Two P/M fabrication routes were used: hot extrusion of the canned and degassed mixtures for the Al 2014 matrix composites and hot forging of CIPed and sintered preforms for the Al 6061 and Alumix 321 matrix composites.

Table 1. Composites produced.

Raw materials	Mean diameter (mm)	Composites	D/d
Al 2014	78.1	Al 2014/SiC F600/10 and 17p	6.0
Al 6061	26.1	Al 2014/SiC F1200/17p	17.0
Alumix 321 AS91	91.2	Al 6061/SiC F600/10 and 20p	2.0
Alumix 321 AS081	32.3	Al 6061/SiC F800/10p	2.6
SiC F600	13.0	Al 6061/SiC F1200/10p	5.7
SiC F800	10.0	321 AS91/SiC F600/10p	7.0
SiC F1200	4.6	321 AS91/SiC F800/10p	9.1
		321 AS91/SiC F1200/10p	19.8
		321 AS081/SiC F800/10p	3.2

$$n = \frac{\pi D^2}{a} = \frac{2\delta}{\delta - \sqrt{\delta^2 - \lambda^2}} \quad (6)$$

where $\lambda = L/d$. Expressing this equation in terms of λ , the distance between ceramic particles relative to their diameter, the following equality is obtained:

$$\lambda^2 = \frac{2}{\delta} \left[\frac{1}{V} - 1 \right] - \frac{1}{\delta^4} \left[\frac{1}{V} - 1 \right]^2 \quad (7)$$

where the second term in the right hand side is only important for values of δ near 1. This expression is graphically represented for several values of the volume fraction of ceramic particles V in Fig. 1.

A more general expression applicable to other particle geometries is obtained by only considering the specific area of the metallic particles A_e and the volume of each ceramic particle V_{cp} :

$$L^2 = \frac{A_e \cdot V_{cp}}{2\alpha} \left[\frac{1}{V} - 1 \right] \quad (8)$$

where αL^2 is the area on the surface of the metallic particles which is allotted to each ceramic particle, α being a geometrical factor ($\alpha = \pi/4$ for spheres).

Consider the predictions of Eqn (7) plotted in Fig. 1:

- For a constant value of the volume fraction of a ceramic powder, with an average particle diameter of d , the plot of the distance between these particles, as a function of the metal particle diameter presents a maximum displaced towards the smaller values of D/d , i.e. for volume fractions between 0.05 and 0.3, D/d at $(L/d)_{\max}$ will change between approximately 3.5 and 2.
- The maximum obviously appears because the model starts to break down for metal and ceramic particles with similar diameters. Above the D/d that gives an $(L/d)_{\max}$ the general behaviour is that of the particles being nearer to each other as the diameter of the metal powder increases relative to the ceramic particles (lower specific area of the metal grains).
- Mixtures for which agglomeration of ceramic particles is less probable are given for the highest values of L/d . The value of $L/d = 1$ refers to the situation in which all the ceramic particles, distributed on the surface of the metal particles, touch the nearest neighbour ceramic particle.
- For each volume fraction there is, therefore, a window of mixtures (range of D/d) for which, ideally, agglomeration of ceramic particles does not occur. The higher the volume fraction of the ceramic powder the narrower this window. For example, at 20% of ceramic, $1.3 < D/d < 8$; at 30%, $1.1 < D/d < 4.6$.
- In the real situation the lower the value of L/d the harder it is to evenly distribute the ceramic particles. Therefore, a more realistic criterium has to be set at a value of $L/d > 1$. If one assumes an arbitrary value of $L/d = 1.5$ then the following table shows how important it is to coordinate grain size distributions and volume fraction.

All the materials were T6 heat treated and tensile tested at room temperature.

Optical metallographic examination was carried out on polished samples of the heat treated composites, in sections parallel to the extrusion or forging direction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile test results are shown in Table 2, each result corresponding to the average of at least three tests. Densities of the as-fabricated materials are also shown in the table.

Table 2. Tensile properties of the heat treated composites

COMPOSITE	Ref. Number	D/d	0.2 PS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Elong. (%)	Theor. dens. (%) as-fabricated
6061/SiC F600/10p	1	2.0	358	380	2.4	99.3
6061/SiC F600/20p	2	2.0	374	395	1.1	98.0
6061/SiC F800/10p	3	2.6	365	395	3.6	99.3
6061/SiC F1200/10p	4	5.7	365	410	3.1	99.3
321 AS081/SiC F800/10p	5	3.2	355	391	3.7	100.0
321 AS91/SiC F600/10p	6	7.0	334	353	1.6	98.0
321 AS91/SiC F800/10p	7	9.1	340	362	2.1	98.6
321 AS91/SiC F1200/10p	8	19.8	240	259	0.8	97.0
2014/SiC F600/10p	9	6.0	466	517	4.1	99.3
2014/SiC F600/17p	10	6.0	459	505	1.6	97.8
2014/SiC F1200/17p	11	17.0	411	439	0.8	95.8

Some of the more relevant microstructures are presented in Fig. 3, in correlation with the appropriate curves resulting from the proposed mixing model. In agreement with the model, a substantial difference in the reinforcement distribution is found between the two composites for which $L/d \leq 1$ and all others. For those two composites, namely 321 AS91/SiC F1200/10p (nr. 8) and Al 2014/SiC F1200/17p (nr. 11), SiC agglomerates to which visible porosity is associated, were frequently found in agreement with the higher global porosity (Fig. 3 and Table 2).

Although in much less amount some SiC agglomerates were visible in the two composites characterized by a L/d of around 1.5 (321 AS91/SiC F800 (nr.7) and Al 2014/SiC F600 (nr.10)) and even less in the 321 AS91/SiC F600 (nr. 6 composite, $L/d \approx 1.7$). All other composites showed a reasonable homogeneous reinforcement distribution associated to a global density of around 100% of the theoretical density (Table 2), with the exception of composite n° 2 that even with a homogeneous distribution showed global porosity of 2% which could be attributed to insufficient forging pressing capacity.

Composites with very high values of D/d (17.0 for the Al 2014/SiC F1200/17p and 19.8 for the 321 AS091/SiC F1200/10p, respectively nr.11 and 9) have significantly lower UTS, 0.2PS and elongation to fracture than the correspondent composites with low values of D/d (respectively nr.10 and 6-7). This is to be expected from the model here introduced which predicts values of L/d near or below unity leading to ceramic particle agglomeration and porosity resulting in degradation of mechanical properties.

Moreover from the theoretical curves of Fig. 3, increasing ceramic content from 10 to 17% for a D/d of about 6 decreases L/d from 1.7 just to over 1.25, thus increasing the agglomeration and porosity. This is the case of the Al 2014 matrix composites; Table 2 and Fig. 4 show that an extra

of 7% in volume of SiC does not add any extra strength to the material (compare composites 9 and 10) and in fact decreases ductility quite substantially.

In the case of the Al 6061 matrix composites with 10% SiC the trend is for improved mechanical properties as the ceramic particle size decreases, as found by other authors [6,7]. It is interesting to note that doubling the concentration of SiC does not have any sizeable effect on the strength of the material and that the ductility is diminished. This is in agreement with the model that predicts a much narrower window of sound mixture in the case of higher ceramic concentration, particularly for values of D/d around and below 2.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A quantitative guideline is now available that allows to select a set of volume fractions and of particle sizes and distributions which has a greater probability of yielding PM MMC's composites with minimized incidence of agglomeration and porosity.
2. Several Al alloy matrix composites display structures and properties which correlate reasonably well with the model here introduced.

REFERENCES

1. J. Parent, J. Iyengar and H. Heinen, Powder blending of metal matrix composites systems, *Advances in Powder Metallurgy* 1989, vol.1 (Proceedings), MPIF, 25-37 (1989).
2. J. H. ter Haar and J. Duszczyk, Mixing of powder metallurgical fibre-reinforced aluminium composites, *Mater. Sci. Eng. A135*, 65-72 (1991).
3. M. H. Carvalho, T. Marcelo, H. Carvalhinhos and C. M. Sellars, Extrusion and mechanical properties of mixed powder and spray co-deposited Al 2014/SiC metal matrix composites, *J. Mater. Sci.* 27, 2101-2109 (1992).
4. M. H. Carvalho, T. Marcelo and H. Carvalhinhos, Compósitos 6061/SiC e Alumix 321/SiC produzidos por pulverometalurgia. Influência do tipo de matriz nas etapas de processamento, *Actas do 6º Encontro da Sociedade Portuguesa de Materiais*, Porto, 27 - 29 October 1993, vol. 1, 513-521 (in portuguese).
5. M. H. Carvalho and H. Carvalhinhos, Closed die PM hot pressed 6061 type Al matrix composites, *Proceedings of the PM'94 Conference*, Paris, 6 - 9 June 1994, vol. III, 1971 - 1974.
6. W. S. Miller, L. A. Lenssen and F. J. Humphreys, The strength, toughness and fracture behaviour in aluminium-lithium based metal matrix composites, *5th International Aluminium-Lithium Conference (Proceedings)*, Williamsburg, USA, 27-31 Mars 1989, MCEP, 931-934.
7. J. Yang, C. Cady, M. Hu, F. Zok, R. Mehrabian and A. Evans, Effects of damage on the flow strength and ductility of a ductile Al alloy reinforced with SiC particulates, *Acta Metall. Mater.* 28, 2613-2619 (1990).

Figure 1. Variation of inter-ceramic particle distance L with ceramic volume fraction and metal powder diameter.

Al 6061

Alumix 321 AS91

Al 2014

SiC F800

Figure 2. Morphology of the particles.

Figure 3. SiC distribution and densities of the various composites, in relation with the model.

Figure 4. Mechanical properties as a function of D/d.